

THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH ROMANTICISM

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Abstract. *This article goes into great depth on the beginnings of the romantic era, how it unfolded, the poets who contributed to its glory, the biographies of these poets, and the specifics of the romantic poetry that dominated this time period. Beginning at the close of the eighteenth century and continuing into the 1930s, the romantic era was marked by various developments. Alexander Pope and other classical poets popularized classical poetry among readers throughout the Neoclassical era, which was succeeded by the romantic era. In the passionately romantic poetry, elements like imagination, emotion, and nature were employed. Romantic poetry made intense use of elements like imagination, emotion, and nature. There were many writers who composed romantic poetry during this time, but only the lives and works of the four major poets—William Wordsworth, Samuel Coleridge, John Keats, and P. B. Shelley—are covered in this article. The earliest romantic period influencers were Wordsworth and Coleridge. People will learn even the smallest details about the romantic era from this article.*

Keywords: *Romantics, neoclassicism, literature, revolution, poetry.*

РАЗВИТИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО РОМАНТИЗМА

Аннотация. *В статье подробно рассматриваются истоки романтической эпохи, ее развитие, поэты, которые способствовали ее славе, биографии этих поэтов, а также специфика романтической поэзии, доминировавшей в этот период. Начиная с конца восемнадцатого века и вплоть до 1930-х годов, романтическая эпоха была отмечена различными событиями. Александр Поуп и другие поэты-классики популяризировали классическую поэзию среди читателей на протяжении всей неоклассической эпохи, на смену которой пришла романтическая эпоха. В страстно-романтической поэзии использовались такие элементы, как воображение, эмоции и природа. Романтическая поэзия интенсивно использовала такие элементы, как воображение, эмоции и природа. В то время было много писателей, сочинявших романтические стихи, но в этой статье рассматриваются только жизнь и творчество четырех крупнейших поэтов — Уильяма Вордсворта, Сэмюэля Кольриджа, Джона Китса и П. Б. Шелли. Самыми ранними*

влиятельными лицами романтического периода были Вордсворт и Кольридж. Из этой статьи люди узнают даже мельчайшие подробности о романтической эпохе.

Ключевые слова: романтика, неоклассицизм, литература, революция, поэзия.

INTRODUCTION

The term "romantic" has grown to imply so many different things that it no longer has any meaning in and of itself, according to American scholar A.O. Lovejoy. The plurality and complexity of European romanticism are reflected in the range of its actual and potential meanings and implications. 11,396 definitions of "romanticism" were counted by F.L. Lucas in *The Decline and Fall of the Romantic Ideal* (1948). Barzun (1961) provides instances of synonymous uses of the term "romantic" in *Classic, Romantic and Modern*, demonstrating that it is arguably the most notable example of a term that may imply several things depending on the needs and preferences of the individual. While "Romantic" is an essential term to describe the most notable writers of the late 18th and early 19th centuries, it is also a little misleading because there was no such thing as a "Romantic movement" at the time, and the greatest writers of the era did not identify as Romantics. A definitive division between the "mechanical" nature of Classicism and the "organic," "plastic" attributes of Romantic art was not made until August Wilhelm von Schlegel's Vienna lectures in 1808–1809.

FINDINGS

Romanticism started in Western Europe, around the middle of the 18th century. At this time, the dominant artistic and cultural movement is Neoclassicism, which finds its inspiration in the aesthetics of ancient civilizations. Neoclassicism values order, self-control, and the promotion of ideal values. The role of romanticism was very important to build nationalists feelings among the Europeans during the nineteenth century. Its aim was to focus on building collective forms of cultural heritage for people to share together with each other. It included traditions, language, cultural aspects. Romanticism emerged in the midst of significant upheavals, wars, and revolutions. Significant political and social restructuring was taking on at the time. Numerous romantic literature addressed the effects of the Industrial Revolution, including the emergence of a new class structure and economy. It is imperative to underscore that a multitude of issues emerged throughout this period. Among the well-known authors are Samuel Coleridge, William Blake, and William Wordsworth. It is hard to overlook the two most significant political revolutions of that era, the American War of Independence (1776–1783) and the French Revolution (1789), which upended established social and political structures, in addition to the

Industrial Revolution. It would be simplistic to approach Blake's poems as more reflections of their era. Romantic literature is typically viewed as escapist because it purposefully uses exaggeration to distance itself from reality. It is also thought to be idealistic and ethereal, idealizing human emotions like love and tenderness. A significant number of romantic poets were also political activists, like Mary Wollstonecraft, who authored *The Vindication of the Rights of Women* (1792) and gave birth to Mary Shelley, who passed away during childbirth. Romanticism is therefore not an escape. Instead, via their works, the poets questioned and attacked the prevailing values. They constantly convey the tensions, hopes, and concerns of living in that era through their poetry, even though they may not always deal with politics directly.

It goes without saying that different poets choose different approaches to convey the fears of their era. Some looked to the future (William Blake) and some to the past (John Keats). Wordsworth studied the countryside as a location where the essence of things and beauty are revealed. In "The Rime of the Ancient Mariner," Coleridge participated in the examination of the inner. This writing makes extensive use of metaphors. A common way to critique social, political, and other evils is through landscapes. The group of people who were romantic poets was not homogenous. The romantics voice disapproval of the social and political environments that currently exist. They center art around the individual, as demonstrated by Lord Byron's *Byronic Hero*.

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